

CONTRIBUTIONS OF THE EXPERT SYSTEMS AND MACHINE LEARNING TECHNIQUES AT THE PRESCRIPTIVE MAINTENANCE LEVEL

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Abstract

Purpose – This paper aims to present the main factors necessary for the implementation of machine learning techniques applied to intelligent systems for the development of prescriptive maintenance systems.

Methodology – Expert systems and machine learning systems have the capacity for ongoing updates and enhancements, enabling organizations to fine-tune their maintenance approaches in response to changing insights and feedback. Industry 4.0 has brought significant contributions in terms of re-engineering prescriptive maintenance systems.

Findings – Expert systems and machine learning techniques complement each other in prescriptive maintenance by leveraging historical data, real-time monitoring and adaptive decision-making to enhance equipment reliability, minimize downtime and optimize maintenance strategies.

Research implications – Both systems can effortlessly incorporate Internet of Things sensors for the acquisition of real-time data, improving the precision and promptness of forecasts and suggestions.

Practical implications – Automated expert systems enhance efficiency, precision and prompt responsiveness in maintenance operations through the application of predetermined rules, analysis of data and decision-making, all accomplished without the need for manual input at each stage.

Originality – This article highlights the significant contributions of expert systems in the context of prescriptive maintenance activities of organizations.

Key words: Prescriptive maintenance, Expert systems, Knowledge acquisition.

Introduction

Prescriptive maintenance is a modern approach to equipment maintenance that goes beyond reactive and preventive maintenance. It uses advanced analytics to predict potential equipment failures and suggests appropriate interventions to avoid them. By combining historical data, real-time sensor information and predictive analytics, prescriptive maintenance allows organizations to take a proactive approach to equipment maintenance, reducing the risk of unplanned downtime and optimizing asset performance (Pop-Suărășan and Ungureanu, 2023). Both from the point of view of expert systems and in the case of the acquisition of technical data specific to production processes, a rapid evolution of decision-making systems can be noted.

Expert systems, a crucial branch of Artificial Intelligence, leverage domain knowledge from subject matter experts and encode it into a knowledge base. These systems excel in diagnosing equipment health, identifying root causes of potential failures and recommending appropriate maintenance actions based on predefined rules and heuristics (Milad et al., 2016). With their sophisticated inference engine, expert systems are the go-to solution for prescriptive maintenance, providing unparalleled diagnostic capabilities and decision-making support.

The combination of expert systems and machine learning techniques is an unbeatable synergy in prescriptive maintenance, delivering comprehensive solutions that leverage the strengths of both paradigms. Expert systems provide interpretability and transparency by incorporating human domain expertise into decision-making processes, while machine learning algorithms enhance predictive accuracy and adaptability by uncovering intricate correlations within data streams (Milad et al., 2016). By integrating these complementary approaches, organizations can achieve operational excellence and gain a competitive edge.

Condition monitoring and fault detection

Condition monitoring systems play a critical role in prescriptive maintenance. These systems continuously monitor equipment health, detect early signs of degradation or malfunction and capture real-time data on key performance indicators (Maillart, 2006).

By applying advanced machine learning techniques, data-driven condition monitoring systems can accurately identify faults or inefficiencies, enabling maintenance personnel to intervene proactively and prevent catastrophic failures. The schema illustrated in Figure 1 presents the flow implementation in forecasting errors. The main components are: the data acquisition phase, data preprocessing, component engineering, model development, deployment phase and model evaluation. It is very important to transform sensor readings into time series data to analyze equipment performance trends and identify patterns and seasonal variations. To forecast errors, it is necessary to select features that have high correlation with past failure events and demonstrate strong predictive performance (Scarf, 2007).

To ensure accurate error prediction, it is crucial to carefully select the appropriate machine learning algorithms, such as regression models, decision trees, or recurrent neural networks, based on the nature of the data and the forecasting horizon. Furthermore, the machine learning models must be trained using historical sensor data and corresponding error occurrences to effectively learn the relationship between sensor readings and error events.

Diagnostic reasoning and fault identification

Expert systems excel in diagnostic reasoning by methodically analyzing symptoms, observations and historical data to identify potential faults or anomalies within equipment systems (Yu et al., 2019). They use rule-based inference engines or Bayesian networks to interpret sensor readings, alarm signals and operational parameters to precisely pinpoint deviations from normal operating conditions. By correlating symptoms with known failure modes and diagnostic patterns, expert systems enable maintenance personnel to accurately identify faults and perform root cause analysis (Gertler, 2021).

Figure 1 Forecasting errors in prescriptive maintenance

To develop and deploy expert systems for maintenance, organizations must follow a structured schema, as illustrated in Figure 2. This schema involves gathering domain-specific knowledge, encoding it into a structured format and developing rules that capture expertise. An inference engine must be implemented to apply rules, interpret sensor readings and incorporate mechanisms for handling uncertainty and ambiguity. To ensure ease of use, an intuitive interface must be designed and visualization tools provided to present diagnostic results.

The expert system must interface with data sources, establish a feedback loop and undergo rigorous testing and validation to ensure reliability and effectiveness. The expert system must then be deployed, integrated into existing maintenance workflows and continuously improved through mechanisms for continuous learning and improvement. Designing a knowledge base for anomaly detection in prescriptive maintenance involves organizing information related to equipment, maintenance activities, historical data, anomaly detection algorithms and providing maintenance recommendations.

Figure 2 Integration of expert systems workflow for prescriptive maintenance strategy

It is crucial to keep track of equipment-related information, including its location, installation date and last maintenance date, as well as maintenance activities performed on each device, including inspections, repairs and calibrations. Sensor data collected from equipment over time must be stored and detected anomalies must be managed, including their type, severity and description. Anomaly detection models must be analyzed, including their algorithms, parameters and performance metrics. The knowledge base must provide maintenance recommendations to ensure optimal equipment performance and improve operational efficiency.

Integration with decision support systems

Expert systems are the key to enhancing diagnostic accuracy and improving recommendation quality. By interfacing with data sources, sensor networks and maintenance management systems, they can access real-time data streams and historical records to provide decision-makers with actionable insights, performance metrics and scenario analysis tools that support informed decision-making and strategic planning (Ungureanu and Ungureanu, 2007). The integration with decision support systems empowers expert systems to enable decision-makers to make informed decisions.

Organizations can develop and deploy expert systems for maintenance by following a specific schema that leverages domain expertise, diagnostic reasoning and decision support capabilities. The knowledge base component gathers domain-specific knowledge, encode it into structured format and develop rules that capture expertise.

The inference engine applies rules to interpret sensor readings, diagnostic information and incorporate mechanisms for handling uncertainty and ambiguity. Organizations must incorporate feedback loops, adaptive learning algorithms and model updating mechanisms to improve the accuracy and reliability of predictive models. This is crucial to ensure that prescriptive maintenance solutions remain agile, responsive and effective in supporting organizational objectives and adapting to dynamic environments.

Interfacing with Internet of Things network or with data sources establish a feedback loop to improve accuracy and relevance of recommendations. The validation and verification component ensure reliability and effectiveness. For the continuous improvement phase, it is necessary to incorporate mechanisms for continuous learning. Designing a knowledge base

for anomaly detection in prescriptive maintenance involves organizing information related to equipment, maintenance activities and historical data and anomaly detection algorithms (Song et al., 2007).

Synergistic integration

The integration of expert systems and machine learning techniques is a highly effective approach to prescriptive maintenance. It combines human knowledge and data-driven insights to optimize asset performance and minimize downtime (Carvalho et al., 2019). By leveraging the strengths of both paradigms, organizations can significantly enhance diagnostic accuracy, improve predictive capabilities and prescribe targeted maintenance actions with unparalleled precision.

Internet of Things technologies can connect various equipment and devices, allowing communication across the maintenance system strategy. Additionally, incorporating automation and robotics technologies can streamline maintenance tasks and improve overall efficiency. Automated systems can handle routine inspections, diagnostics and repairs, freeing up human resources for more complex tasks and helping to reduce the risk of human error.

The prescriptive maintenance is built on the foundation of predictive analytics, which uses historical data, real-time information and sensor readings to anticipate equipment failures before they occur. Machine learning algorithms like regression models, neural networks and decision trees analyze potential faults or performance degradation. Predictive analytics detects anomalies and deviations from normal operating conditions, empowering maintenance teams to proactively address potential issues, thereby avoiding costly breakdowns and optimizing the lifespan of assets (Zonta et al., 2020).

Advanced machine learning algorithms, including regression models, neural networks and decision trees, analyze vast datasets to identify patterns indicative of impending faults or performance degradation. The power of predictive analytics lies in its ability to detect anomalies and deviations from normal operating conditions, allowing maintenance teams to take preemptive action and avert costly breakdowns while optimizing asset lifespan.

Context-aware decision-making

Synergistic integration is essential for prescriptive maintenance systems to make context-aware decisions. Expert systems provide the framework for incorporating domain knowledge and contextual constraints, ensuring that maintenance recommendations are tailored to specific equipment configurations, operational requirements and organizational priorities.

By integrating machine learning techniques for real-time data analysis and anomaly detection, prescriptive maintenance systems can dynamically adjust maintenance strategies based on current conditions and emerging risks, maximizing asset uptime and reliability. Figure 3 presents a logical representation of context-aware decision-making in the context of prescriptive maintenance tasks.

Figure 3 Logical representation of context-aware decision-making for prescriptive maintenance

Context-aware decision-making for prescriptive maintenance is a powerful approach that involves combining rules, algorithms and data-driven models. By leveraging this approach, the maintenance engineers can take decisions based on the system's current context to ensure proactive and efficient maintenance strategies. This approach comprises context parameters, rule-based logic, machine learning models, a decision engine and a feedback loop. To assess the current state of a system, it is necessary to consider various parameters such as sensor data (temperature, vibration, pressure readings from different sensors), environmental factors (humidity, ambient temperature) and operational data (usage patterns, workload, previous performance).

These parameters contribute to understanding the system's condition and identifying any potential issues. Machine learning algorithms can be used to analyze historical data and predict future system behavior (Geurtsen et al., 2023). These models can identify patterns, anomalies and trends to anticipate maintenance needs. Some common techniques include predictive maintenance models, which forecast equipment failures or degradation based on past behavior and anomaly detection, which identifies deviations from normal operating conditions that may indicate impending issues.

This engine is designed to prioritize and optimize maintenance schedules based on several factors, such as the criticality of the equipment, cost considerations and resource availability. The engine will prioritize maintenance for mission-critical components to minimize downtime and repair costs by scheduling maintenance during planned downtimes or off-peak hours.

Leveraging Machine Learning techniques

Machine learning techniques are an exceptional tool for detecting anomalies and monitoring the conditions of industrial equipment. They can identify even the slightest deviations from normal operating conditions, which may indicate potential equipment failures or performance degradation. Unsupervised learning algorithms, such as clustering and anomaly detection algorithms, analyze sensor data streams to detect outliers and anomalous patterns that may indicate faults or inefficiencies (Jordan and Mitchell, 2015). By continuously monitoring equipment health in real-time, machine learning-based condition monitoring systems enable proactive maintenance interventions and preemptive fault mitigation.

The algorithm presented in Table 1 is suitable for continuous monitoring of incoming data from a sensor. It involves maintaining a buffer to store recent data points. For each iteration, statistics such as mean and standard deviation are calculated over a set of data points. The latest data point is then compared to these statistics to determine if it is anomalous.

Table 1. Anomaly detection algorithm

Steps	Explanation
	Threshold variables
	Standard deviation Sd , Percentage change Pc
Input	Data analysis parameters
	Number of data points Nd , Time duration t
	Buffer size Bf for storing recent data
1.	Initialize parameters and thresholds
	Loop
2.	Continuously monitor incoming data
3.	Read data point from sensor
4.	Add data point to buffer
5.	If $Bf > Nd$
5.1.	Calculate statistics Sd
5.2.	Check if the latest data point is atypical
5.2.1.	Compute deviation of the latest data point
5.2.2.	If deviation > threshold
5.2.2.1.	Log anomaly
6.	Repeat loop
7.	End loop

If the deviation of the latest data point from the mean exceeds a predefined threshold, an anomaly is logged. This algorithm represents a basic anomaly detection algorithm and may need to be adapted or extended based on specific requirements, such as the type of sensor data, the nature of anomalies and the desired sensitivity of the detection.

Conclusion

Expert systems and machine learning have revolutionized prescriptive maintenance, empowering organizations to predict equipment failures, prescribe optimal maintenance actions and maximize asset performance. The combination of human expertise and data-driven insights has enabled industries to transcend reactive approaches and embrace a proactive maintenance paradigm that fosters resilience, efficiency and competitiveness in an increasingly dynamic environment.

The integration of expert systems with machine learning and other emerging technologies promises to unlock new opportunities for proactive asset management and predictive maintenance optimization. Machine learning empowers organizations to make data-driven decisions that drive productivity, reliability and cost-effectiveness. With the integration of data driven analytics and predictive modeling, machine learning technologies can unlock new frontiers in prescriptive maintenance optimization, promoting innovation and competitiveness in diverse industries.

As technology continues to evolve, the integration of expert systems with emerging technologies such as machine learning and Internet of Things promises to unlock new frontiers in prescriptive maintenance optimization, driving innovation and sustainable growth across diverse sectors. Prescriptive maintenance solutions harness the power of predictive analytics, condition monitoring and optimization algorithms to anticipate equipment failures and optimize resource allocation, thereby maximizing operational efficiency and minimizing downtime.

This article highlights the pivotal role of expert systems in advancing prescriptive maintenance strategies and emphasizes their significant contributions to organizational success. Also, this article represents an academic approach in the context of doctoral studies. By combining the interpretability of expert systems with the predictive power of machine learning, organizations can develop prescriptive maintenance solutions that leverage human expertise, data-driven insights and adaptive learning to enhance operational efficiency. The synergy between expert systems and machine learning will play a critical role in driving innovation and enabling proactive asset management in diverse industries as prescriptive maintenance continues to evolve. As future developments, both the development of a system model based on specific machine learning algorithms and the implementation of a routine related to expert systems will be taken into account.

Notes

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